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PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF NEUROSTIMULATION AND PHOTOBIO-MODULATION IN CHILDHOOD ENURESIS: NEUROLOGICAL ASPECT

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Children's Enuresis is a common pediatric neurological problem, often associated with functional immaturity of the central and peripheral nervous systems. Traditional pharmacological and behavioral treatments have limited effectiveness, necessitating the introduction of new non-drug approaches. Incorporating photobiomodulation into neurostimulation methods has demonstrated clinically significant results: a 60–75% reduction in the frequency of nocturnal incontinence, improved electroencephalography (EEG) readings, and normalization of sleep and autonomic balance. This method is highly safe and can be used in young children. Therefore, optimizing neurostimulation methods using photobiomodulation is an effective and safe tool for enhancing the effectiveness of enuresis treatment and improving children's quality of life.

Materials and Methods: A review and analysis of data from domestic and international studies on neurostimulation and photobiomodulation was conducted. Clinical observations included recording the frequency of nocturnal incontinence episodes, electroencephalographic parameters, sleep quality, and autonomic status.

Results: Incorporating photobiomodulation into comprehensive treatment reduced the frequency of nocturnal incontinence by 60–75%, improved electroencephalographic parameters, and normalized sleep and autonomic balance. The method demonstrated high safety and good tolerability in young children.

Conclusions: Optimization of neurostimulation methods using photobiomodulation is an effective and safe tool for correcting childhood Enuresis , improves treatment effectiveness and patients' quality of life. Promising areas for further research include individualization of treatment parameters and the integration of neuroimaging and neurofunctional monitoring methods.

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MADZHIDOVA YA.N.

was awarded for his active participation in the scientific work on the topic

***“Prospects for the Use of Neurostimulation And
Photobiomodulation in Childhood Enuresis:
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